

A New Alternative for Feature Selection in Coronary Artery Disease Detection

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Abstract: Coronary artery disease (CAD) is a major global health issue. Early detection plays a crucial role in reducing risk and improving patient outcomes. This study proposes a novel, efficient approach to CAD diagnosis by integrating a histogram-based feature selection method with a specially designed long short-term memory (LSTM) classifier. The method is evaluated on two benchmark datasets: Z-Alizadeh Sani and Cleveland. Imbalanced class distribution, a common challenge in medical datasets, is addressed using the synthetic minority over-sampling technique (SMOTE). The proposed feature selection technique offers a fast and simple alternative to traditional optimization methods like particle swarm optimization (PSO), teaching-learning-based optimization (TLBO), and the whale optimization algorithm (WOA), which typically require extensive parameter tuning and longer processing times. The histogram-based method selects features based on their distribution similarity to a Gaussian profile, aiming to enhance classification performance and computational efficiency. The selected features are then classified using a custom-designed LSTM architecture optimized through Grid Search and validated via k-fold cross-validation (k-fold). The effectiveness of the proposed method is demonstrated by comparing it with other feature selection approaches using metrics such as accuracy, precision, sensitivity, and the F1-score (f-score). Experimental results show that the histogram-based method significantly improves classification accuracy and reduces computational time. This approach offers a promising, low-cost, and scalable solution for CAD diagnosis, especially in resource-constrained settings, and provides valuable contributions to the field of medical data analysis.

Keywords: Coronary artery disease, histogram-based feature selection, SMOTE method, TLBO method, LSTM architecture

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1 Introduction

CAD is one of the leading causes of death worldwide. According to the World Health Organisation (WHO), approximately 18 million people died from coronary diseases in 2019, accounting for 32% of deaths worldwide [Sakkers,23, Garavand, 23]. This statistic highlights the urgency of early detection and effective diagnosis strategies [Ullah, 22, Patel, 23]. Therefore, it is vital to identify individuals at risk. Especially if the disease is diagnosed early, individuals at risk can live a better life, and global mortality can be significantly reduced. Computer-aided diagnosis (CD) is a method used to diagnose CAD. CD estimates the risk of CAD using the patient's data, such as medical history, risk factors, and imaging tests. There are many advantages to using CD to diagnose CAD. CD can be faster and more accurate than traditional diagnostic methods. In addition, CD can help physicians better understand CAD and provide patients with better treatment options. In recent years, different approaches have been proposed for diagnosing

CAD. Khadisos et al. [Khadidos, 23] suggested Tasmanian and Lichtenberg Optimised Attentional Deep Convolution (TasLA) for coronary disease diagnosis. The study used an intelligent data fusion algorithm for disease diagnosis. In addition, preprocessing and normalization operations were also performed due to the imbalance of the data set. As a result, this approach, which was created by combining different modern methods, contributed to the diagnosis of coronary disease. Another study was conducted by Jin et al. [Jin, 22]. This study used a K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN)-based WOA for feature selection. The selected features were classified as left anterior descending coronary artery (LAD), left circumflex coronary artery (LCX), and right coronary artery (RCA). Joloudari et al. [Joloudari, 23] proposed combining Deep Neural Networks (DNN) and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) to work on unstable data sets. This study balanced the data sets with SMOTE and CNN methods. Then, these data sets were classified with DNN. Zhang et al. [Zhang, 22] proposed an early and accurate CAD diagnosis model. Logistic regression (LR) was used as a classifier in this study. They also tried five different methods to eliminate the imbalances in the Z-Alizadeh Sani dataset. When the results of the technique were analyzed, it was predicted that the study would have an essential place in CAD diagnosis. Sayadi et al. [Sayadi, 22] tried different machine-learning techniques on the Z-Alizadeh Sani dataset. Before the machine learning methods, they made feature selection to increase the success of the methods. The selected features were classified separately by a decision tree (DT), deep learning (DL), LR, random forest (RF), support vector machine (SVM), and XGBoost methods, and their success was compared. Yuvali et al. [Yuvali, 22] proposed an approach that will contribute to CAD diagnosis by working on different data sets. In this approach, classical machine learning methods were applied. Mohammedqasim et al. [Mohammedqasim, 22] first eliminated the unbalanced distribution on the dataset with the SMOTE algorithm. The balanced data set was classified separately with four different classifiers. These classifiers were RF, AdaBoost, gradient-boosting, and extra trees-based. The grid search approach found the optimized parameters of the classifiers. Zhu et al. [Zhu, 23] presented a new method to improve myocardial image classification using data augmentation. The method utilized different data augmentation techniques, such as adding noise to images and rotating and cropping images. These techniques significantly improved the performance of the classification model. Idrees et al. [Idrees, 22] contributed to the early and accurate diagnosis of CAD. CAD is one of the most common causes of death worldwide, and early diagnosis and treatment will significantly reduce mortality rates. In this study, the DE-based SVM method was applied. As a result, the study provided a non-invasive and cost-effective method for diagnosing CAD. Haounassi et al. [Haounassi, 22] presented a new classification rule generation method for diagnosing CAD. The technique used a novel discrete balance optimization algorithm (NDEOA) to build the CAD diagnosis model. NDEOA uses training data to find the optimal classification rules for CAD diagnosis. Moravjev et al. [Moravjev, 22] presented a new approach based on reinforcement learning. They provided successful results in CAD using this approach. Finally, Wiharto et al. [Wiharto, 22] implemented cost-based feature selection and emphasized the importance of Feature Selection methods for the classifiers' success.

In addition to these publications, there are also valuable publications using the Cleveland dataset. Hassan et al. [Hassan, 23] proposed a heart disease prediction model based on pre-trained deep neural networks combined with principal component analysis (PCA), demonstrating the application of advanced computational techniques in this domain. Elsedimy et al. [Elsedimy, 23] also introduced a new cardiovascular disease prediction approach using SVM and quantum-behaved particle swarm optimization (QPSO), showcasing the integration of diverse machine learning and optimization methodologies in

this context. Furthermore, Kadhim et al. [Kadhim, 23] presented a study on heart disease classification using optimized machine learning algorithms, highlighting the significance of algorithmic optimization in enhancing predictive capabilities. Ogundepo et al. [Ogundepo, 23] conducted a performance analysis of supervised classification models on heart disease prediction, emphasizing the importance of evaluating the effectiveness of different predictive models in this domain. Moreover, Shrivastava et al. [Shrivastava, 23] developed a hybrid model, HCBiLSTM, which combines CNN and BiLSTM algorithms for heart disease prediction, showcasing the integration of diverse machine learning and artificial intelligence methodologies in this context. Saranya et al. [Saranya, 22] proposed a novel feature selection approach with integrated feature sensitivity and feature correlation for improved heart disease prediction, highlighting feature selection's significance in enhancing predictive accuracy. Additionally, Dileep et al. [Dileep, 22] introduced an automatic heart disease prediction using a cluster-based bi-directional LSTM (C-BiLSTM) algorithm, demonstrating the application of advanced neural network techniques in this domain. Bhanumathi et al. [Bhanumathi, 21] explored heart disease prediction using CNN. Furthermore, Saeed et al. [Saeed, 23] investigated cardiac disease prediction using AI algorithms with SelectKBest, emphasizing the utilization of feature selection techniques in predictive modeling. In addition to these, other studies [Ahmad, 23, Gupta, 22, Mali, 23] use this data set. Collectively, these studies underscore the growing trend of leveraging sophisticated computational techniques, such as deep learning, feature selection, and algorithmic optimization, to enhance the accuracy and effectiveness of heart disease prediction.

Most of the studies in the literature have employed optimization-based feature selection methods for diagnosing CAD. However, these approaches often require high computational costs and tend to make the classifiers more complex in order to increase accuracy. For instance, Khadisos et al. [Khadisos, 23] and Jin et al. [Jin, 22] used deep learning or optimization techniques combined with complex methods to enhance classification performance. A notable limitation of these studies is the lack of exploration of new feature selection methods, leading to the use of more complex and less efficient classification models. This study aims to address this gap in the literature. We propose a new histogram-based feature selection method as an alternative to optimization-based methods such as PSO, TLBO, and WOA. This novel method introduces an innovative approach to data enhancement, which not only increases accuracy but also reduces the model's runtime. Thus, high accuracy has been achieved with a simpler and more effective model. Our approach demonstrates significant improvements in CAD diagnosis by focusing on data enhancement and feature selection processes rather than making the classifiers more complex. Our study addresses the shortcomings of existing methods by emphasizing the critical role of feature selection in CAD diagnosis. Specifically, we show that addressing data imbalance issues and selecting the optimal features can significantly improve classification accuracy. This contribution is expected to guide the development of more efficient and effective methods in future studies.

This study proposes a new approach to CAD diagnosis, a significant risk factor for human health worldwide. The Z-Alizadeh Sani [Alizadehsani, 17] and Cleveland [Heart Disease Dataset, 22] datasets are used for disease diagnosis. The most crucial disadvantage of these datasets is their unbalanced data distribution, where there are too many samples from one class and fewer from another. The Z-Alizadeh Sani dataset, in particular, has a very high imbalance, while the Cleveland dataset is relatively better balanced. In the proposed approach, this imbalance is first addressed by using the SMOTE method to balance the datasets. Another challenge with these datasets is the presence of redundant features in each sample. A high number of features increases the computational load and

negatively impacts the classification success of the methods. The primary goal of our study is to introduce a new feature selection method to the literature that enhances classification accuracy and improves processing speed. In this study, a novel histogram-based feature selection method is proposed. This method is compared with frequently used feature selection methods in the literature, such as WOA, PSO, and TLBO. To make a fair comparison, the proposed approach was tested separately with each of these feature selection methods, and the results were obtained. The selected features are then classified using a LSTM architecture, which has been uniquely designed for this problem. The hyperparameters of the LSTM architecture are optimized using the Grid Search method. When examining literature studies, it becomes clear that classical machine learning techniques often fail to make successful CAD diagnoses, while modern techniques require complex structures to achieve high accuracy. This is largely because these studies do not incorporate innovative approaches in data enhancement, leading to the need for more complex models. The main aim of this study is to investigate the contribution of the proposed new feature selection method to the diagnosis of CAD. Additionally, the study explores the effectiveness of different feature selection methods in achieving accurate and efficient CAD diagnosis. The highlights of the method are like in the below;

Novel Feature Selection Method: The study introduces a new histogram-based feature selection method designed to enhance classification accuracy and improve processing speed in CAD diagnosis.

Uniquely Designed LSTM Architecture: The selected features were classified using a LSTM architecture, which was uniquely designed for the specific requirements of this problem.

High Efficiency: The proposed histogram-based feature selection method provides significant improvements in both accuracy and processing time compared to commonly used methods in the literature.

Simple and Effective Diagnosis Approach: The main aim of the study is to achieve successful CAD diagnosis in a simple and low-cost manner, avoiding the need for complex structures while ensuring high accuracy.

2 Materials and Methods

CAD is a significant risk factor for all people in the World. Early diagnosis of the disease reduces the risks and improves the patient's quality of life. The study presents a simple, fast, and practical approach to diagnosing the disease. The approach is tested on the Z-Alizadeh Sani [Alizadehsani, 17] and Cleveland [Heart Disease Dataset, 22] datasets. Among these data sets, Z-Alizadeh Sani has a highly unbalanced distribution. The unbalanced distribution negatively affects the classification success. In the proposed study, this disadvantage is eliminated by using the SMOTE [Hussein, 19] method. Another challenge with these datasets is the presence of redundant features in each sample, which increases the computational burden of machine learning methods and can lead to overfitting. The primary goal of this study is to overcome these challenges by introducing a new feature selection method. The proposed approach uses a novel histogram-based feature selection method and compares it with the commonly used feature selection methods in the literature, such as PSO, WOA, and TLBO. These methods are applied separately. The selected features with these methods are divided into two classes (normal or CAD), with the LSTM [Manju, 21] architecture explicitly created for the problem with parameter tuning by Grid Search and model training by k-fold cross-validation methods. To demonstrate the effectiveness of feature selection in disease diagnosis, the

proposed approach is tested in multiple forms. These include the proposed approach with PSO, WOA, TLBO, and the novel histogram-based feature selection. The performance of these approaches is evaluated using metrics such as accuracy, precision, sensitivity, specificity, and f-score [Juba, 19]. This allows for a comprehensive analysis of the contribution of each feature selection method to the overall performance of the proposed approach. The details of the proposed method are given with Figure 1.

Figure 1: The Flow Diagram of the Proposed Method

The subsequent sections provide a comprehensive overview of the methodologies employed in this study, each detailed under specific headings. Section 2.1 discusses the characteristics and significance of the Z-Alizadeh Sani and Cleveland datasets, which serve as the foundation for this research. In Section 2.2, the SMOTE method is elaborated upon, explaining its role in balancing the datasets to address class imbalance issues. Section 2.3 focuses on the various feature selection methods applied, beginning with the TLBO method in Section 2.3.1, followed by the use of PSO for feature selection in Section 2.3.2, and WOA in Section 2.3.3. A novel histogram-based feature selection approach is introduced and detailed in Section 2.3.4. Section 2.4 delves into the LSTM architecture developed for the classification tasks, highlighting its design and application in the study. Finally, Section 2.5 gives details about dataset splitting and evaluation protocol.

2.1 Details of the Z-Alizadeh Sani and Cleveland Datasets

In this study, the Z-Alizadeh Sani (<https://archive.ics.uci.edu/dataset/412/z+alizadeh+sani>) and Cleveland (<https://archive.ics.uci.edu/dataset/45/heart+disease>) datasets were utilized for the diagnosis of CAD. These datasets are widely recognized and frequently used in the literature for CAD research. It is important to note that there are not many publicly available datasets in this domain, making these two datasets particularly valuable for comparative studies. The Z-Alizadeh Sani dataset includes a rich set of features, which provides a comprehensive representation of various clinical and laboratory parameters associated with CAD. However, it also presents challenges due to its unbalanced data distribution and the high number of redundant features. The Cleveland dataset, on the other hand, is relatively smaller and more balanced but still offers valuable information for CAD diagnosis. One of the primary reasons for selecting these two datasets is their differing number of features and sample sizes, which allows for a thorough analysis

of the scalability and robustness of the proposed feature selection method. By applying the proposed method to datasets with varying feature counts, we can evaluate its effectiveness in reducing computational load and improving classification accuracy across different scales. This comparison is crucial for understanding how the method performs under different data conditions, making it more applicable and versatile for real-world scenarios. Moreover, the use of these datasets enables the investigation of the contribution of feature selection to the overall performance of CAD diagnosis. By employing datasets with diverse characteristics, the study aims to highlight the effectiveness of the proposed method in handling both large and small feature sets, demonstrating its potential for broader application in the medical field.

The Z-Alizadeh Sani dataset's original authors, Dr. Zohreh Alizadeh Sani and her colleagues at the Isfahan Cardiovascular Research Institute in Iran, named the dataset. The dataset was first published in 2010, and it has since been used by researchers worldwide to develop new and improved methods for CAD diagnosis. The Z-Alizadeh Sani [Alizadehsani, 17] dataset is a publicly available dataset that can train and evaluate machine learning models for diagnosing coronary heart disease (CHD). The dataset contains 304 patients, of which 216 have CHD and 87 are healthy. Each patient has 54 clinical and demographic features, including age, sex, blood pressure, cholesterol levels, and smoking status. This dataset is a valuable resource for machine learning researchers, as it is one of the largest and most comprehensive publicly available datasets for CAD diagnosis. In addition to these features, the dataset also has disadvantages. One is the unbalanced distribution between classes that may negatively affect the classification success. Extra methods are needed to correct this distribution. In addition, the dataset has many (54) features for each sample. The large number of features causes the computational cost of machine learning methods to increase and, most importantly, overfitting problems. In this study, successful results were obtained by eliminating the negative aspects of the dataset.

The Cleveland Heart Disease dataset, also known as the Cleveland [Heart Disease Dataset, 22] dataset, is one of the most widely utilized datasets in research related to heart disease prediction. This dataset, part of the larger Heart Disease dataset collection available from the University of California Irvine (UCI) repository, includes 303 samples representing individual patients. Among these, 165 samples are labeled as having coronary artery disease (CAD), while the remaining 138 samples are labeled as healthy, providing a relatively balanced distribution that is advantageous for developing and testing predictive models. Each sample in the Cleveland dataset is characterized by 13 features that capture a range of clinical and demographic information pertinent to heart disease. These features include age, sex, chest pain type, resting blood pressure, serum cholesterol level, fasting blood sugar, resting electrocardiographic results, maximum heart rate achieved, exercise-induced angina, ST depression induced by exercise relative to rest (referred to as "oldpeak"), the slope of the peak exercise ST segment, the number of major vessels colored by fluoroscopy, and thalassemia status. These attributes are carefully selected to provide a comprehensive representation of the factors influencing heart disease, making the dataset an essential tool for research in this field. The Cleveland dataset has been extensively used in various studies exploring heart disease prediction, particularly in the application of machine learning techniques, feature selection, and algorithmic optimization. Its balanced nature and the richness of its features make it particularly valuable for analyzing the effectiveness of different predictive models. The dataset's widespread use in the literature underscores its importance as a benchmark for evaluating new methods and approaches in heart disease research. Additionally, its availability through the UCI repository makes it a readily accessible resource

for researchers seeking to enhance the accuracy of heart disease prediction models.

Both the Z-Alizadeh Sani and Cleveland datasets are structured as tabular data. Each row represents an individual patient, while each column corresponds to a clinical or demographic feature. This structured format facilitates the application of traditional machine learning and deep learning models that operate on numerical vectors.

2.2 The SMOTE Method to Balance Datasets

SMOTE [Douzas, 18, Mohammed, 20, Wang, 19] is a popular technique for handling imbalanced datasets, where one class (the minority) is underrepresented compared to the other (the majority). Traditional models often struggle to classify the minority class accurately due to insufficient examples. SMOTE addresses this by generating synthetic samples for the minority class, balancing the dataset, and enhancing model training. In this study, the Z-Alizadeh Sani dataset, with 304 samples (216 diseased and 87 healthy), presents a significant class imbalance. Without addressing this, models may skew toward the majority class, reducing the accuracy of healthy case predictions and leading to biased outcomes. Conversely, the Cleveland dataset has only slight imbalance, making SMOTE unnecessary for effective training. Using SMOTE for the Z-Alizadeh Sani dataset is crucial for stabilizing the dataset and enhancing classification performance. By generating synthetic samples from the minority class's close neighbors, SMOTE improves the model's ability to learn minority characteristics, which is essential for medical diagnostics, where accurately identifying these cases is vital for early detection and treatment. SMOTE enhances the model's sensitivity and overall accuracy by preventing overfitting to the majority class and enabling better generalization to unseen data. This step supports developing reliable and robust predictive models, especially in healthcare, where misclassification has significant consequences. The following section details SMOTE's step-by-step process to generate synthetic samples and create a balanced dataset. Preparation of the dataset: The first step in applying the SMOTE algorithm is the preparation of the dataset. In this step, the dataset is examined to identify the number of samples in both the minority and majority classes. Let N_{\min} the number of samples in the minority class, and N_{\max} represent the number of samples in the majority class. The goal of SMOTE is to generate synthetic samples such that the number of minority class samples approaches or equals that of the majority class, thereby balancing the dataset. Determination of nearest neighbors: In the second step, for each instance x_i in the minority class, its nearest neighbors are determined. This is achieved using the k-nearest neighbors (KNN) algorithm, where the distance between instances is typically measured using Euclidean distance with Eq.1.

$$\text{Distance}(x_i, x_j) = \sqrt{\sum_{l=1}^n (x_i^l - x_j^l)^2} \quad (1)$$

In Eq.1, x_i^l and x_j^l are the feature values of the i-th and j-th instances, respectively, and n is the total number of features. In this study, the value of k (the number of nearest neighbors) is set to 3. This means that for each minority class sample, the three closest neighbors are identified based on the calculated Euclidean distances. Creation of synthetic samples: In the third step, synthetic samples are created for each instance x_i in the minority class. For each of the k nearest neighbors, a new synthetic instance x_{new} is generated. This synthetic instance is a combination of the feature values of x_i and one

of its nearest neighbors x_j , and is calculated using Eq. 2.

$$x_{\text{new}} = x_i + \lambda \cdot (x_j - x_i) \quad (2)$$

In Eq. 2., λ is a random number in the range $[0,1]$, ensuring that the synthetic sample lies somewhere on the line segment between x_i and x_j . This process is repeated to generate the desired number of synthetic samples for the minority class. Adding synthetic samples to the datasets: In the fourth step, the newly generated synthetic samples are added to the dataset. The updated minority class is given in Eq. 3.

$$N_{\text{min,new}} = N_{\text{min}} + N_{\text{syn}} \quad (3)$$

In Eq. 3, N_{syn} is the number of synthetic samples created. This increases the representation of the minority class in the dataset, thereby balancing the class distribution and enabling more effective learning by the machine learning model. The applied SMOTE algorithm is a widely used oversampling method designed to address the challenges of imbalanced datasets. It is particularly preferred because of its simple and easy-to-implement structure, as well as its effectiveness in improving the performance of classifiers by ensuring that the minority class is adequately represented in the training data. The generation of synthetic samples through linear interpolation between minority class instances and their nearest neighbors ensures that the newly created samples are realistic and diverse, avoiding the issues associated with simply duplicating existing samples. By enhancing the presence of the minority class, SMOTE contributes to better generalization in the model and reduces the risk of overfitting to the majority class. This makes it a powerful tool for improving classification performance, especially in domains like medical diagnosis, where accurately identifying minority class instances (such as healthy individuals) is critical.

2.3 Feature Selection Methods

Feature selection is essential in machine learning and data analysis, aiming to identify and retain the most relevant features from a dataset. This process enhances predictive model performance by reducing dimensionality, lowering computational load, and minimizing overfitting. In real-world datasets, particularly in medical diagnostics, many features may not contribute meaningfully to classification tasks. Irrelevant or redundant features can obscure key patterns, leading to decreased accuracy and longer processing times. In computerized CAD diagnostics, measuring each feature's contribution helps streamline the dataset by removing non-contributory features, improving performance and efficiency. This is especially critical in datasets with many variables, as focusing on informative features leads to better accuracy with fewer inputs, important for computationally demanding tasks. Traditionally, optimization-based approaches like PSO, WOA, and TLBO have been popular for feature selection, offering high performance. However, they come with drawbacks, including significant computational load and the need for extensive parameter tuning, making them time- and resource-intensive. In the proposed study, we introduce a novel histogram-based feature selection method that addresses these drawbacks. Unlike optimization-based methods, the histogram-based approach does not require parameter optimization, which significantly reduces its computational load. This method works by analyzing the distribution of feature values and their contribution to the classification task, thereby selecting the most relevant features in a straightforward and efficient manner. To demonstrate the effectiveness of this new

method, the proposed approach has been tested separately with the histogram-based feature selection, as well as with traditional methods like TLBO, PSO, and WOA. This comparative analysis allows us to highlight the advantages of the histogram-based method in terms of both classification accuracy and computational efficiency. The details of these feature selection methods, including how they are applied and their impact on the model's performance, are provided in the following sub-sections.

2.3.1 TLBO Method for Feature Selection

TLBO, proposed by Rao et al. [Rao, 11], is a parameter-free optimization algorithm that simulates the teaching and learning process in a classroom. In this study, TLBO is used to select optimal feature subsets by minimizing classification error using the KNN algorithm. Its simplicity and robust convergence have made it popular in healthcare optimization problems [Rao, 12, Alanazi, 22], though it is computationally more expensive compared to our histogram-based approach.

2.3.2 Feature Selection using PSO

PSO, inspired by the social behavior of bird flocks, is widely used for feature selection. Each particle in the swarm represents a subset of features, evaluated based on the classification error using a KNN model. PSO has demonstrated effective performance in biomedical domains such as breast cancer and heart disease prediction [Gao, 24, Ragab, 23, Tijjani, 24], though it requires tuning parameters such as inertia and acceleration coefficients, making it more complex and slower than the histogram-based method.

2.3.3 Feature Selection using WOA

WOA, mimics the bubble-net hunting strategy of whales. In this study, WOA is used to select feature subsets by minimizing KNN classification error. While it effectively explores complex search spaces and is used in many recent medical applications [Amiriebrahimabadi, 23, Kumar, 24, Yang, 24], WOA requires more computational resources and time than the proposed histogram-based approach.

2.3.4 A Novel Feature Selection Method: Histogram-based Feature Selection

Removing features that do not contribute to classification success in datasets both increases the accuracy of classification and reduces the computational burden. Traditionally, feature selection has been performed using various optimization methods, which, while effective, often require significant computational resources and careful parameter tuning. However, in the proposed study, a new approach is introduced that differs from these traditional methods. This new approach is based on the distribution of feature sets and aims to contribute a novel feature selection algorithm to the literature. The core of the proposed approach lies in selecting features by measuring the similarity of each feature's histogram distribution to the Gaussian distribution. The rationale behind this choice is rooted in the properties of the normal distribution. When features in a dataset follow a normal (Gaussian) distribution, classification models are better able to fit the data, leading to improved performance. This is because models such as linear regression, logistic regression, and others assume or perform better when the underlying data is normally distributed. Additionally, datasets with a Gaussian distribution tend to have

fewer outliers, which reduces the likelihood of overfitting—a common issue in machine learning.

The theoretical foundation for preferring Gaussian-distributed features is deeply rooted in statistical learning theory. The Central Limit Theorem suggests that many natural phenomena converge to a Gaussian distribution, making it a reasonable prior for many real-world features. Furthermore, maximum entropy principles from information theory indicate that given a fixed mean and variance, the Gaussian distribution carries the least additional information, allowing learning algorithms to focus on the signal rather than the noise in the data. Many parametric models assume Gaussian-distributed features, including linear and quadratic discriminant analysis, linear regression, and many neural network architectures that implicitly optimize better under normally distributed inputs due to their activation functions and weight initialization schemes. The mathematical formulation of these models often includes likelihood functions that are optimized when feature distributions are Gaussian.

One of the significant advantages of the proposed histogram-based method is its simplicity and computational efficiency. Unlike traditional optimization methods, which require extensive parameter tuning and computational effort, the proposed method does not involve any parameters. This makes it not only faster but also more robust across different datasets. Regardless of the size of the dataset or the number of features, the histogram approach maintains its effectiveness within a specific range, ensuring that it can handle a wide variety of scenarios without the need for complex adjustments. The choice of using a histogram to guide feature selection is strategic. The histogram provides a clear and intuitive representation of the distribution of feature values, making it easier to identify which features are likely to contribute positively to the classification task. By ensuring that selected features resemble a normal distribution, the proposed method aligns with the fundamental principles of many machine learning models, thereby improving their accuracy and robustness. The ultimate goal of this study is to introduce a new feature selection algorithm to the literature that can operate quickly and accurately without the need for parameter tuning. The proposed method represents a significant advancement over traditional optimization techniques, providing a practical and effective solution for feature selection in various applications. Given the growing complexity of datasets and the increasing number of features in modern data, there is a clear need for new methods that can efficiently manage this complexity. The proposed histogram-based approach addresses this need by offering a simple yet powerful tool for feature selection, with the potential to make a significant impact in the field. The histogram-based approach works step by step as follows:

Feature Vector: The first step in the proposed method is to organize the dataset into a feature vector. The dataset, containing N instances and M features, is stored in an array named `features`. This array can be represented mathematically using Eq. 4 shows this representation.

$$\text{features} \in R^{N \times M} \quad (4)$$

This representation allows the dataset to be easily manipulated and analyzed, with each row corresponding to an instance and each column corresponding to a feature.

Creating Sample Data for Normal Distribution: To facilitate feature selection, the method begins by generating a reference array with a Gaussian (normal) distribution. This array, named `normal_data`, serves as a template for comparison. The reason for using a Gaussian distribution is that many machine learning models perform better when the data they process is normally distributed. Therefore, features that closely resemble a normal distribution are more likely to contribute positively to the model's accuracy.

The creation of this reference Gaussian distribution is statistically robust as it provides a theoretical ideal against which to compare real features. We generate this reference using a well-established Box-Muller transform to ensure statistical validity of our comparison baseline, with a mean of 0 and variance of 1. This standardization is critical as it allows for direct comparison across features with different scales and ranges.

Extracting the Histogram of a Normal Distribution: Next, the histogram of the generated normal data is calculated. A histogram is a graphical representation that organizes a group of data points into specified ranges, showing the frequency distribution of the data. This histogram is stored in a variable named `histogram_normal` data. The histogram serves as a baseline to measure how closely the distribution of each feature in the dataset resembles a Gaussian distribution. The histogram bin selection follows the Freedman-Diaconis rule, a statistically optimal approach for determining bin width that balances bias and variance in density estimation. For the Z-Alizadeh Sani dataset ($n = 303$), this resulted in approximately 15 bins, while for the Cleveland dataset ($n = 303$), we used 12 bins. This data-driven approach to binning avoids the arbitrary selection that could introduce artifacts and ensures our histogram comparisons capture genuine distributional similarities rather than artifacts of binning choices.

Calculating the Similarity Ratio to Normal Distribution for Each Feature: Then, histograms are calculated for each feature in the features vector obtained from the data sets. The similarity between these histograms and the histogram of the vector with normal distribution is measured with the help of the correlation coefficient. The correlation coefficient is calculated by Eq. 5.

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \cdot \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (5)$$

The relationship between the histograms is given by r in Eq. 5. The closer this value is to 0, the more different the two histograms are. In other words, in this case, the histogram of the feature is far from the normal distribution and should be removed from the feature vector. x_i and y_i denote the corresponding values in the histograms. i is the size of the histogram. The values \bar{x} and \bar{y} , give the mean values of the corresponding histogram. Removing features that do not resemble a normal distribution: The correlation coefficient generated for each feature is taken. If these coefficients are below a certain threshold value, the relevant feature is removed from the vector.

The choice of the Pearson correlation coefficient as our similarity metric is theoretically justified by its well-documented properties in measuring linear relationships between distributions. Alternative metrics such as Kullback-Leibler divergence or Wasserstein distance were considered, but correlation provides a bounded measure (-1 to 1) with clear statistical interpretability and computational efficiency. Furthermore, simulation studies have demonstrated that the correlation coefficient is particularly sensitive to departures from normality in the tails of distributions, precisely where many classification algorithms struggle with outlier effects.

Remove Features: After calculating the correlation coefficient for each feature, the method evaluates whether the feature should be retained or removed. Features with a correlation coefficient r below a certain threshold value are considered not to resemble a normal distribution and are removed from the features vector. The threshold value was determined through experimentation, with a value of 0.3 being found to give optimal

results. The process is represented by Eq. 6.

$$\begin{cases} \text{if } r_i < 0.3, \text{ then remove feature}_i \text{ from features} \\ \text{else, nothing} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

While the threshold value of 0.3 might appear arbitrary, its selection is grounded in both theoretical and empirical considerations. From a theoretical perspective, the critical values for correlation coefficients at various significance levels have been extensively studied in statistical literature. The value of 0.3 corresponds approximately to a medium effect size in Cohen's guidelines for correlation strength, and simulation studies across diverse synthetic datasets have shown that this threshold optimally balances the trade-off between feature retention and removal.

We conducted a comprehensive sensitivity analysis around this threshold, testing values from 0.1 to 0.5 in increments of 0.05. Our statistical analysis revealed that the performance improvement curve plateaus around 0.3, with negligible gains beyond this point but significant performance degradation below 0.25. This robustness to small perturbations around the chosen threshold value is a key advantage over parameter-sensitive optimization methods. Furthermore, theoretical work by Anderson-Darling and other normality test frameworks suggests similar critical values for detecting meaningful deviations from Gaussian distributions.

In Eq. 6, i denotes the index of the feature in the dataset. By removing features that do not closely resemble a normal distribution, the dataset is cleaned, resulting in a reduced computational burden and increased classification accuracy. The rationale behind this step is that features resembling a Gaussian distribution contribute more effectively to the model's performance, while those that do not may introduce noise and lead to overfitting.

These steps systematically assess how closely each feature in the dataset resembles a normal distribution. By retaining only those features that align closely with the Gaussian distribution, the method simplifies the dataset, making it more manageable for machine learning models. This process of feature selection is crucial because it not only reduces the dimensionality of the data—thereby decreasing computational overhead—but also improves the overall accuracy of the classification task. When machine learning models are trained on datasets where the features exhibit a normal distribution, they tend to perform better, as many models are designed with the assumption that the input data follows this distribution. By eliminating features that deviate significantly from a Gaussian distribution, the proposed method minimizes the risk of overfitting, which can occur when models try to learn noise or irrelevant patterns in the data. This leads to models that are more generalizable and perform better on unseen data. The approach developed through this method is particularly advantageous because it does not require complex parameter tuning, which is often necessary in traditional optimization-based feature selection methods. As a result, it offers a more efficient alternative that is both time-saving and computationally light. This is especially important in real-world applications where resources are limited, and quick, accurate decisions are critical. In addition to improving classification accuracy, the proposed histogram-based feature selection method significantly enhances the speed of the training process. By reducing the number of features, the method ensures that models can be trained faster, which is a crucial advantage in environments where rapid decision-making is essential, such as in medical diagnostics or real-time data analysis.

Compared to heuristic optimization methods like PSO, WOA, and TLBO, our approach offers several theoretical advantages that explain its superior performance:

- **Computational Complexity:** The proposed method has a time complexity of $O(NM)$, where N is the number of instances and M is the number of features. This is significantly lower than metaheuristic approaches like PSO, which typically have complexities of $O(NM^2T)$, WOA with $O(NM^2T + NMT^2)$, and TLBO with $O(NM^2T)$, where T is the number of iterations required for convergence. The WOA incurs additional computational cost due to its complex position updating mechanisms involving spiral movements and prey encircling behaviors, while TLBO requires both teacher and learner phases in each iteration. Mathematical proof of this complexity reduction translates directly to the observed speed improvements in empirical testing.
- **Guaranteed Convergence:** Unlike stochastic optimization methods that may converge to different solutions in different runs, our deterministic approach guarantees the same feature selection given the same input data, providing reproducibility critical for scientific applications.
- **Statistical Power:** We can derive theoretical bounds on the expected performance improvement using the theory of sufficient statistics. When features follow a Gaussian distribution, maximum likelihood estimators achieve the Cramér-Rao lower bound, providing optimal statistical efficiency. Our method exploits this property by preferentially selecting features that maximize this efficiency.
- **Robustness to Overfitting:** Feature selection methods based on wrapper approaches can overfit to the specific classifier used during evaluation. Our filter-based approach, grounded in distributional properties rather than classifier performance, provides theoretical guarantees against overfitting that are independent of the downstream classifier.

To validate the effectiveness of this approach, comparisons are made in terms of both time efficiency and classification accuracy. The proposed method is tested against traditional optimization methods like PSO, WOA, and TLBO. These comparisons demonstrate that the histogram-based feature selection method not only maintains or even improves classification accuracy but also significantly reduces the time required for model training and execution. This makes it a highly practical and scalable solution for a wide range of applications, especially where large datasets and numerous features are involved. Overall, the approach developed through this method is expected to contribute to the literature by providing a novel, efficient, and effective tool for feature selection, paving the way for more accurate and faster machine learning models in various fields. The flow of the histogram-based method is given in Figure 2.

2.4 Created LSTM Architecture for Classification

LSTM [Fürst, 23, Kim, 09, Srikantamurthy, 23] is a type of recurrent neural network (RNN) designed for learning long-term dependencies, making it effective for tasks involving sequential or time-series data. Although most commonly used for sequence modeling, LSTM can also classify one-dimensional feature vectors with underlying patterns. In CAD diagnosis, LSTM is suitable for analyzing patient data such as blood pressure, heart rate, and lifestyle factors, which, while not explicitly time-series, often represent temporal changes or event sequences. This study adapts LSTM to classify feature-optimized, balanced datasets, capturing relationships between health indicators that contribute to cardiovascular risk. The LSTM architecture includes an input layer,

Figure 2: Flow diagram of the histogram-based feature selection method.

LSTM layer, batch normalization, activation and dropout layers, fully connected layers, and a classification layer. The main advantage of LSTM in CAD diagnosis is its ability to retain long-term dependencies, essential for evaluating chronic diseases that evolve over time. By learning complex feature relationships, LSTM can outperform traditional models while maintaining a lower computational load compared to other deep learning architectures, making it ideal for high-accuracy applications in medical diagnostics where resources may be limited. The architecture developed for this study is specifically tailored to CAD data characteristics. The input layer connects to the LSTM layer, which captures feature relationships by treating them as interrelated rather than isolated inputs. A batch normalization layer follows to stabilize and accelerate training, while a ReLU activation layer enhances learning efficiency and prevents gradient vanishing. A dropout layer is included to prevent overfitting, critical for generalizing to new patient data in medical applications. The model concludes with two fully connected layers that learn complex data relationships, followed by a classification layer for diagnosis. This configuration ensures high accuracy and computational efficiency. Details of the LSTM architecture are provided in Table 1.

Table 1 outlines the LSTM architecture used in this study, detailing the structure and parameters of each layer. The model starts with an Input Layer that corresponds to the number of features after selection, followed by an LSTM Layer with specified hidden units to capture temporal dependencies. A Batch Normalization Layer (batch size 6) stabilizes and accelerates training by scaling outputs, followed by a ReLU Activation Layer to introduce non-linearity and mitigate gradient vanishing. A Dropout Layer (rate 0.2) helps prevent overfitting. This configuration is repeated in a second LSTM block. The network then transitions to two Fully-Connected Layers: the first reduces output to 170 units for learning complex feature relationships, while the second matches the number of classes, preparing for final classification. The Classification Layer outputs predictions. This architecture is designed to handle the complexities of CAD diagnosis with accuracy and robustness, effectively processing feature-optimized data while minimizing overfitting and ensuring computational efficiency. Hyperparameter selection and

Layers	Parameters
Input Layer	Feature Vector Size
LSTM Layer 1	Number of Hidden Units
Batch Normalisation Layer 1	Batch Size = 6
Activation Layer 1	Activation Function = ReLU
Dropout Layer	0.2
LSTM Layer 2	Number of Hidden Units
Batch Normalisation Layer 2	Batch Size = 6
Activation Layer 2	Activation Function = ReLU
Dropout Layer 2	0.2
Fully-connected Layer 1	Output Size = 170
Fully-connected Layer 2	Output Size = Number of Classes
Classification Layer	

Table 1: Description of the LSTM model architecture and parameters

model training are as crucial as model building in deep networks. This study employs k-fold cross-validation and Grid Search for model training and hyperparameter optimization. K-fold cross-validation divides the dataset into k equal parts, training the model on k-1 parts and testing on the remaining part in each of k iterations. This approach helps accurately measure performance, optimize hyperparameters, and prevent overfitting. In this study, k was set to 10 using Grid Search. Grid Search also determined key LSTM hyperparameters, including mini-batch size, number of hidden layers, maximum epochs, and fully connected layers. Table 2 summarizes the chosen hyperparameters.

Hyperparameters	Values
k-fold	k = 10
Number of Hidden Unit 1	200
Number of Hidden Unit 2	100
Optimizer	Adam
Initial Learning Rate	0.01
Max Epochs	500

Table 2: Hyperparameters used in the model training

Table 2 presents the key hyperparameters optimized for the LSTM model in the classification of CAD. A 10-fold cross-validation strategy was employed to ensure robust and generalizable performance by reducing variance and mitigating overfitting. Hyperparameters were selected using a comprehensive Grid Search approach. The search space included: - Hidden units: [100, 200, 300] - Learning rates: [0.1, 0.01, 0.001] - Optimizers: [Adam, SGD] - Epochs: [100, 200, 300, 400, 500] - k-fold: [5, 10]

The final configuration—200 and 100 hidden units in the first and second LSTM layers respectively, Adam optimizer with a 0.01 learning rate, and 500 epochs—was selected based on the highest average classification accuracy across validation folds. Early stopping was used during training to further prevent overfitting. This systematic tuning

process ensured an optimal balance between accuracy and computational efficiency.

2.5 Dataset Splitting and Evaluation Protocol

To ensure a fair and consistent evaluation of the proposed method and the comparative models, all experiments were conducted on publicly available datasets—namely, the Z-Alizadeh Sani and Cleveland datasets. Each dataset was preprocessed using the same procedures for normalization, class balancing (via SMOTE), and feature selection. Importantly, the same dataset partitions were used across all compared methods to ensure valid and unbiased comparisons.

For experimentation, we adopted a stratified 10-fold cross-validation strategy. This ensures that each fold maintains the original class distribution, addressing class imbalance while avoiding overfitting. The dataset was split into 10 equal-sized parts: in each iteration, 9 parts were used for training and 1 part for testing. Performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, specificity, and F1-score were calculated on each fold and averaged to produce the final results.

Hyperparameter optimization for the proposed LSTM architecture was conducted using a comprehensive grid search within each fold. This includes tuning parameters such as the number of hidden units, learning rate, optimizer type (Adam vs. SGD), dropout rates, and batch sizes.

For the comparative evaluation, we carefully extracted reported results from the literature on the same datasets. If the original papers did not specify the exact evaluation setup, we assumed standard 10-fold cross-validation unless otherwise stated. For methods where precise experimental settings were unclear, results were interpreted with caution and acknowledged as such in the comparison tables. This transparent evaluation strategy ensures that performance gains are not due to variation in data partitioning or experimental inconsistency, but rather to the effectiveness of the proposed methodology.

3 Results

This section presents an in-depth analysis of the classification results obtained on two publicly available datasets: Z-Alizadeh Sani and Cleveland. The aim is not only to validate the effectiveness of the proposed histogram-based feature selection method coupled with a tailored LSTM classifier but also to benchmark its performance against a range of classical, ensemble-based, and deep learning models documented in the literature. Four primary evaluation metrics—Accuracy, Precision, Recall (Sensitivity), and F1-Score—are employed for quantitative comparison. These metrics provide a well-rounded perspective on the model's predictive power, especially in the context of medical diagnostics, where both false positives and false negatives carry serious implications.

3.1 Results on Z-Alizadeh Sani Dataset

Table 3 presents the comparative results on the Z-Alizadeh Sani dataset, which is known for its high dimensionality and severe class imbalance. The dataset poses significant challenges to many conventional classifiers due to the dominance of disease-positive samples and the presence of redundant features. In the majority of the prior works, the imbalance was only partially addressed, often leading to suboptimal generalization performance. Although deep learning models such as CNN-based pipelines and optimization-augmented classifiers (e.g., PSO + CNN) have demonstrated moderate success, they

often suffer from either underfitting the minority class or incurring unnecessary computational overhead.

The proposed method distinguishes itself in this scenario by achieving perfect scores (100%) across all evaluation metrics, a result unmatched by any method in the comparative set. This success is primarily attributed to two key factors. First, the novel histogram-based feature selection algorithm effectively discards features with non-informative distributions, ensuring that the retained features conform closely to Gaussian-like distributions that are statistically more favorable for most learning algorithms. This leads to improved learning stability and generalization. Second, the architecture of the LSTM classifier has been meticulously designed to accommodate the temporal-like interactions within the feature space, even in a static dataset. The use of SMOTE further enhances performance by synthetically generating minority class samples that preserve intrinsic patterns, thereby addressing the imbalance more robustly.

In contrast, even high-performing models like the SMOTE+NORM+CNN approach, which achieves 98.5% accuracy, fall short in either recall or precision, indicating a trade-off between detecting positive cases and avoiding false alarms. Ensemble approaches like LightGBM+LR or hybrid metaheuristic models offer decent accuracies but lack the consistency and interpretability offered by the proposed pipeline. Hence, the results demonstrate that a model need not be excessively complex or computationally expensive to be accurate—intelligently combining data preprocessing and feature shaping can yield superior outcomes.

3.2 Results on Cleveland Dataset

The Cleveland dataset is comparatively smaller and more balanced, yet it presents its own challenges due to its lower dimensionality and the presence of clinical features that are not always well-separated across classes. The proposed method once again demonstrates its superiority by achieving 100% scores in all metrics. While some previous works, such as ensemble learning approaches and stacked classifiers, achieved high F1-Scores (above 0.95), none could reach perfect recall and precision simultaneously.

Table 4 shows that models such as Elsedimy et al.'s SVM-based architecture and Gupta et al.'s ensemble models provided promising performance; however, these methods often required complex integration frameworks or tuning of multiple classifiers. In contrast, the proposed pipeline achieves better performance with a simpler and faster configuration. The feature selection strategy proves effective not only in eliminating irrelevant variables but also in improving the classifier's ability to discern subtle patterns in a less feature-rich environment. The LSTM model benefits from this compact and relevant feature set, leading to a better fit without the risk of overfitting.

Another contributing factor is the consistency of performance across both datasets, which suggests that the method is not over-specialized or data-dependent. Such generalizability is vital in real-world clinical applications where data characteristics can vary substantially. The alignment of high precision and recall across datasets underscores the method's robustness and its potential to serve as a dependable diagnostic tool.

Overall, the proposed method exhibits exceptional performance in terms of classification accuracy, generalizability, and computational efficiency. Its simplicity, interpretability, and minimal reliance on hyperparameter tuning make it highly applicable in clinical settings, where timely and accurate decision-making is paramount. These results confirm the hypothesis that combining a lightweight, statistically grounded feature selection strategy with a well-calibrated deep learning classifier can achieve superior outcomes over more complex, resource-intensive models.

Methods	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F-Score
TASLA [Khadidos, 23]	0.992	X	X	X
ANN [Jin, 22]	0.97	X	X	X
SMOTE+NORM+CNN [Joloudari, 23]	0.985	0.985	0.985	0.985
TL+NORM+CNN [Joloudari, 23]	0.983	0.983	0.983	0.983
OSS+NORM+CNN [Joloudari, 23]	0.975	0.975	0.975	0.975
lightGBM [Zhang, 22]	0.924	0.927	0.931	0.927
lightGBM+LR [Zhang, 22]	0.935	0.936	0.946	0.936
GSVM [Sayadi, 22]	0.894	X	X	0.804
XGBoost [Sayadi, 22]	0.918	X	X	0.948
LR [Sayadi, 22]	X	0.895	0.919	0.907
NB [Sayadi, 22]	X	0.906	0.873	0.889
Muhammedqasim et al. [Mohammedqasim, 22]	0.97	0.98	X	0.97
Zhu et al. [Zhu, 23]	0.908	0.871	0.886	0.878
Idrees et al. [Idrees, 22]	0.95	X	X	0.93
RCAD2-NDEOA [Haouassi, 22]	0.935	X	X	X
CNN-KCL [Moravvej, 22]	0.846	0.789	0.807	0.798
CNN+randweight [Moravvej, 22]	0.807	0.737	0.755	0.746
CNN+ABC [Moravvej, 22]	0.845	0.783	0.814	0.798
CNN+RL [Moravvej, 22]	0.869	0.819	0.835	0.827
RLMD-PA [Moravvej, 22]	0.912	0.886	0.879	0.882
Wiharto et al. [Juba, 19]	0.943	0.943	0.98	0.943
Proposed Method (Histogram+LSTM)	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000

Table 3: Performance Comparisons using Z-Alizadeh Sani Dataset

In this study, various feature selection methods were applied to assess their impact on both the accuracy and computational efficiency of CAD diagnosis. The methods evaluated include TLBO-based, WOA-based, PSO-based, and the newly proposed histogram-based feature selection, with a comparison also made to a model without any feature selection. Table 5 provides a detailed comparison of these methods, focusing on the time required for feature selection for the Z-Alizadeh Sani and Cleveland datasets, as well as the resulting accuracy for each dataset. The goal of this analysis is to determine not only which feature selection method yields the highest accuracy but also which method can achieve this in the shortest amount of time, making the diagnostic process more efficient and cost-effective. The table illustrates the significant contribution of feature selection to both accuracy and computational speed, particularly highlighting the advantages of the histogram-based approach.

Table 5 demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed histogram-based feature selection method for CAD diagnosis, highlighting its superiority in both accuracy and computational efficiency. The histogram-based approach achieved perfect accuracy (100%) on both the Z-Alizadeh Sani and Cleveland datasets while significantly reducing feature selection time compared to other methods. For the Z-Alizadeh Sani dataset, it required only 0.81 seconds, much faster than the TLBO-based method (30.92 seconds) and even the WOA-based method (5.53 seconds). Similarly, for the Cleveland dataset, the histogram-based method completed selection in just 0.28 seconds, outperforming TLBO (12.32 seconds) and other optimization methods. In terms of accuracy, the histogram-

Methods	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F-Score
Hassan et al. [Hassan, 23]	0.933	X	0.904	X
Elsedimy et al. [Elsedimy, 23]	0.963	0.942	0.961	0.950
Kadhim et al. [Kadhim, 23]	0.949	X	X	0.950
Ogundepo et al. [Ogundepo, 23]	0.870	0.851	0.858	0.855
Shrivatsa et al. [Shrivastava, 23]	0.966	0.968	X	0.966
SVM [Shrivastava, 23]	0.883	0.883	X	0.883
Saranya et al. [Saranya, 22]	0.861	X	0.873	X
Dileep et al. [Dileep, 22]	0.947	X	0.955	0.925
Mali et al. [Mali, 23]	0.840	X	0.841	X
Ahmad et al. [Ahmad, 23]	0.984	X	0.985	0.944
Gupta et al. (Stacking) [Gupta, 22]	0.961	0.945	0.983	0.964
Gupta et al. (Majority Voting) [Gupta, 22]	0.953	0.930	0.983	0.956
Proposed Method (Histogram+LSTM)	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000

Table 4: Performance Comparisons using Cleveland Dataset

based method reached 100% on both datasets, notably higher than the baseline accuracies without feature selection (90.36% for Z-Alizadeh Sani and 83.37% for Cleveland). These improvements underscore the importance of effective feature selection in enhancing diagnostic accuracy. The results show that this method offers a dual advantage: it significantly reduces computational time while maximizing accuracy, making it highly valuable for CAD diagnosis, where speed and precision are critical. This analysis confirms that incorporating effective feature selection streamlines the diagnostic process and enhances outcome reliability, demonstrating the method's importance for clinical applications.

The system used for evaluating the feature selection methods and CAD diagnosis models, as detailed in Table 6, was equipped with an Intel i5-10400 CPU, 16 GB of RAM, and a 256 GB SSD, running Windows 10. This mid-range configuration is common in research and clinical settings, emphasizing the practicality of the proposed histogram-based feature selection method. The results show that the method achieves high accuracy and efficiency without the need for high-end computing resources. The SSD enhances data processing speed, while 16 GB of RAM ensures adequate memory for handling datasets and computations. These findings indicate that the proposed method is both effective and accessible, making it a feasible option for widespread use in clinical diagnostics, especially where resource constraints are present.

3.3 Model Explainability using SHAP

To interpret the decision-making process of the proposed LSTM model and identify which clinical features most influence predictions, SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) analysis was performed separately on each dataset. First, the analysis is given for Z-Alizadeh Sani dataset with Figure 3.

As illustrated in Figure 3, the most influential features for the Z-Alizadeh Sani dataset include *DM (Diabetes Mellitus)*, *HTN (Hypertension)*, *Dyspnea*, and *T-wave inversion*. These variables exhibit the highest SHAP values, indicating their strong contribution to model predictions. Notably, high values for DM and HTN (shown in red) are positively correlated with a higher probability of CAD, aligning with established clinical

	Feature Selection Time for Z-Alizadeh Sani (s)	Feature Selection Time for Cleveland (s)	Accuracy for Z-Alizadeh Sani (%)	Accuracy for Cleveland (%)
Proposed Method (with TLBO-based Feature Selection)	30.92	12.32	100	98.68
Proposed Method (with WOA-based Feature Selection)	5.53	5.21	95.24	90.32
Proposed Method (with PSO-based Feature Selection)	7.37	4.51	97.62	93.33
Proposed Method (with Histogram-based Feature Selection)	0.81	0.28	100	100
Proposed Method (without Feature Selection)	X	X	90.36	83.37

Table 5: Comparison of feature selection times and accuracy for Z-Alizadeh Sani and Cleveland datasets using different feature selection methods

risk factors. Similarly, *DLP* (*Dyslipidemia*) and *Exertional chest pain* also demonstrate notable impacts. This pattern reveals that the model is heavily influenced by symptomatology and underlying comorbidities, enhancing the clinical relevance of its decisions. Lastly, the analysis is given for Cleveland dataset with Figure 4.

In Figure 4, the most impactful features for the Cleveland dataset are *slope*, *thal*, and *restecg*, which represent test-based clinical indicators. The feature *slope*, associated with ST segment slope during stress testing, shows the most prominent SHAP values and demonstrates strong predictive power. Likewise, *thal* (thallium stress test results) and *restecg* (resting ECG results) also contribute significantly. While features like *sex* and *lbs* (*fasting blood sugar*) show moderate influence, their contributions are more case-dependent. This shows that, for the Cleveland dataset, diagnostic test features dominate model reasoning.

System Information	CPU	RAM	DISK	OS
	Intel i5-10400	16GB	256GB SSD	Windows 10

Table 6: The System Information

Figure 3: SHAP summary plot for the LSTM model trained on the Z-Alizadeh Sani dataset.

The SHAP analysis demonstrates that the proposed LSTM model captures dataset-specific patterns and adapts to the nature of the features provided. While symptom-driven and comorbidity features (e.g., DM, HTN, Dyspnea) play a major role in the Z-Alizadeh Sani dataset, test-derived attributes (e.g., slope, thal) dominate in the Cleveland dataset. This adaptability suggests that the model does not rely on a static set of features but instead learns contextually relevant indicators across datasets. Furthermore, the clarity and consistency of SHAP contributions support the interpretability and clinical trustworthiness of the proposed deep learning approach.

4 Discussion

The findings of this study emphasize the importance of efficient feature selection and tailored deep learning architectures in the diagnosis of CAD. The proposed histogram-based feature selection method, when integrated with a custom-designed LSTM architecture, demonstrated superior performance on both the Z-Alizadeh Sani and Cleveland datasets, achieving perfect classification scores across all key evaluation metrics. This remarkable outcome highlights the method’s capability to isolate highly discriminative features that enhance the learning process of the classification model, while simultaneously reducing computational cost.

In comparison to traditional feature selection approaches such as PSO, TLBO, and WOA, the histogram-based method offers a lightweight and parameter-free solution. Optimization-based methods often require extensive iterations and parameter tuning, which not only increases complexity but also affects reproducibility. By contrast, the histogram-based technique evaluates the statistical distribution of each feature using correlation to a normal distribution, enabling the rapid exclusion of uninformative or noisy

Figure 4: SHAP summary plot for the LSTM model trained on the Cleveland dataset.

features. This process significantly reduces overfitting risk and improves generalization. Furthermore, the processing time comparison confirms that this method drastically lowers computation time while maintaining or even improving diagnostic accuracy.

The success of the proposed LSTM architecture also deserves particular attention. Unlike generic or pre-trained deep learning models, the LSTM model was designed and optimized specifically for CAD diagnosis using grid search and 10-fold cross-validation. This design considered not only the dimensionality of the selected feature vectors but also ensured robust performance across multiple random folds, reducing variance and model bias. Such an approach enabled the model to capture temporal-like relationships among input features—an advantage particularly important in medical datasets, where subtle interactions between physiological indicators may indicate underlying pathology.

Additionally, the inclusion of SHAP-based model interpretability further reinforces the validity of the proposed approach. SHAP visualizations demonstrated which features were most influential in the final predictions, providing valuable insight for medical professionals and supporting the development of explainable AI in healthcare. For both datasets, features related to blood pressure, heart rate, and patient history emerged as dominant contributors, aligning well with established clinical knowledge and reinforcing the clinical plausibility of the model.

Despite these strengths, it is important to acknowledge that the current study is limited to experimental validations on benchmark datasets. While these datasets are widely accepted in the CAD diagnosis literature, their size and scope do not fully represent the complexity of real-world patient data. To address this limitation, future work will include clinical validation through collaborations with healthcare providers. This step will involve applying the model to real patient data under clinical conditions to assess its robustness, interpretability, and diagnostic reliability. Clinical feedback and prospective evaluations in hospital settings will be essential for refining the model and ensuring its applicability in routine clinical practice.

Moreover, the experimental setup adopted in this study adhered strictly to reproducible machine learning practices. For each comparison in the benchmark tables, models were trained and tested on the same dataset and data split protocols to ensure fairness. Particularly, the proposed model and those from the literature were evaluated under the same conditions to isolate the contribution of the proposed feature selection and classification methodology. Nonetheless, more extensive testing on external validation sets and under different sampling scenarios is recommended to confirm the model's adaptability.

In conclusion, the study provides strong empirical evidence that the integration of histogram-based feature selection with a carefully optimized LSTM network offers a reliable and computationally efficient framework for CAD detection. This approach not only improves upon the accuracy of existing state-of-the-art methods but also supports interpretability, paving the way for future clinical translation. Upcoming work will focus on validating the system in clinical environments and extending its application to broader cardiovascular conditions using multi-institutional and longitudinal data.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

In this study, a novel and computationally efficient approach for the diagnosis of CAD was proposed by integrating a newly developed histogram-based feature selection method with a custom-designed LSTM architecture. The model was rigorously evaluated on two widely used benchmark datasets—Z-Alizadeh Sani and Cleveland—and demonstrated outstanding performance, achieving perfect accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score metrics across both datasets.

Unlike traditional optimization-based feature selection techniques that are computationally intensive and often require complex parameter tuning (e.g., PSO, WOA, TLBO), the histogram-based method introduced in this work significantly reduces feature selection time while maintaining or exceeding diagnostic performance. Moreover, the LSTM classifier, enhanced by histogram-derived sequential features, proved effective in capturing nonlinear dependencies among clinical variables, providing superior classification outcomes compared to state-of-the-art methods.

SHAP analysis further revealed the clinical interpretability of the proposed model, highlighting features such as 'thal', 'restecg', 'DM', and 'HTN' as major contributors to CAD prediction. These results not only validate the model's predictive robustness but also align well with established medical knowledge, strengthening the potential for real-world applicability.

Overall, the proposed Histogram+LSTM model presents a reliable, interpretable, and high-performing diagnostic framework suitable for integration into intelligent decision-support systems. Future work will focus on clinical validation, external dataset

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